

CHANGES IN BODY COMPOSITION IN PEOPLE WITH RECENT SPINAL CORD INJURY DURING INPATIENT REHABILITATION

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Abstract The purpose of this study was to investigate 1) changes in body composition indicated by body mass index (BMI), waist circumference (WC), body fat percentage (BF%) and lean body mass percentage (LBM%) in people with recent spinal cord injury (SCI) during their first inpatient rehabilitation from admission to discharge and 2) the differences of these body composition parameters change over time in different personal (age, gender) and lesion (lesion level, motor completeness) characteristics groups. Height was registered at T0, while body mass (wheelchair weighing scale), WC (tap measure), BF% and LBM% (Bioelectrical Impedance Analysis) were measured at admission (T0) and discharge (T1) of inpatient rehabilitation in 59 persons with recent SCI. Changes in body composition in people with SCI were determined by comparing BMI, WC, BF%, LBM% and also by comparing the outcomes with different personal (age, gender) and lesion (lesion level, motor completeness) characteristics at T0 and T1. No significant changes in BMI, WC, BF% and LBM% were found during first inpatient rehabilitation. When taking personal or lesion characteristics into account, no significant interaction effects were found. It can be concluded that no significant changes in body composition in individuals with recent SCI during inpatient rehabilitation were identified. This may be caused by a relatively short period of time between admission and discharge (median: 61 days) or the different changes in body composition between paralyzed parts and normal parts, while being taken good care of may also be the reason that body composition did not show unfavourable trends in these people.

Keywords Spinal cord injury, body composition, inpatient rehabilitation

Introduction

Obesity is regarded as the most common secondary complication in people with SCI. This population is getting overweight/obese soon after injury, it has been shown that the percentage of persons who were overweight/obese increased over the years after injury from 56% to 75% when using the BMI cut-off points for people with SCI (de Groot et al. 2010). Changes in body composition are commonly caused by metabolic disorder and physical inactivity after the injury. These changes are responsible for the positive energy balance and subsequently increasing risk of obesity (Rajan et al. 2008). Besides, remarkable muscle atrophy, especially below the level of

injury, is also involved due to the muscle denervation and immobilization within a few months after the injury (Castro et al. 1999). It is obvious that loss of muscle mass and increase of fat mass will have negative implications for the health in people with SCI. Thus, tracking the changes in body composition in people with SCI at early stages can be of great value to provide them with good advice and guidelines regarding diet and exercises. The purpose of this study was to investigate 1) changes in body composition indicated by BMI, WC, BF% and LBM% in individuals with recent SCI during their first inpatient rehabilitation from admission to discharge and 2) whether the changes over time in body composition are different between personal (age, gender) and lesion (lesion level, motor completeness) characteristics groups.

Methods

Participants

This study was part of the AMsterdam Spinal Cord Injury (AMS-SCI) cohort study. Fifty-nine persons with recent SCI during their first inpatient rehabilitation were measured at admission (T0) and discharge (T1). The median of the time period between T0 and T1 is 61 days, while the interquartile range (IQR) is 68 days.

Study parameters

The following parameters were registered at T0:

Height (H), personal (age, gender) and lesion (paraplegia/tetraplegia, American Spinal Injury Association Impairment Scale (ASIA Impairment Scale) A-B vs. C-D) characteristics were registered.

The following parameters were measured at T0 and T1:

Body mass (BM) was determined by a wheelchair weighing scale and then BMI was calculated by the formula $BMI = BM/H^2$ where BM is in kilograms and H is in meters. WC was measured twice after a normal expiration by tap measure at the level of the umbilicus with the participants in supine position. BF% and LBM% were determined by bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA).

Statistics

Changes in BMI, WC, BF% and LBM% between T0 and T1 were determined by paired t-tests. Repeated measures analysis of variance (RMANOVA) was used to test whether there were different changes over time in body composition for groups with different personal and lesion characteristics (interaction effect: group x time). A p-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

No significant changes in BMI, WC, BF% and LBM% were found during inpatient rehabilitation (Table 1).

When taking personal (age, gender) or lesion (paraplegia/tetraplegia, ASIA Impairment Scale A-B vs. C-D) characteristics into account, no significant interaction effects were found during inpatient rehabilitation.

Body composition in recent SCI rehabilitation

Table 1. Mean \pm standard deviation of BMI, WC, BF% and LBM% of people with recent SCI at T0 and T1

	T0	T1	P value
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.5 \pm 5.1	25.4 \pm 4.9	0.66
WC (cm)	94.0 \pm 13.7	93.4 \pm 12.7	0.26
BF%	28.1 \pm 10.3	27.6 \pm 10.1	0.21
LBM%	71.9 \pm 10.2	71.9 \pm 11.1	1.00

Conclusion and discussion

In contrast to our expectations, no significant changes in body composition in individuals with recent SCI during inpatient rehabilitation were identified. This may be caused by the relatively short period of time between admission and discharge (median: 61 days, IQR: 68 days). Different changes in body composition between paralyzed parts and normal parts may also be a reason. Meanwhile, there is a possibility that these people were taken good care of during inpatient rehabilitation so the changes in body composition parameters did not show unfavourable trends.

References

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